

Grosseteste's Law of Refraction

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Robert Grosseteste was one of the most prominent thinkers of the Thirteenth Century. In the framework of the Aristotelian physics and under the influence of a Neoplatonic outlook, Grosseteste wrote several scientific treatises, mainly concerning some problems of optics, acoustic and the causes of heat. Here we discuss the laws of reflection and refraction of light, as proposed in one of his treatises, the De Iride. In particular, we will consider his law of refraction.

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Robert Grosseteste (c.1175 – 1253) was one of the most prominent thinkers of the Thirteenth Century. Philosopher and scientist, he was Bishop of Lincoln from 1235 to 1253. Grosseteste drew from Augustine his Neoplatonic outlook; in his philosophical thought, he made also extensive use of the works of Aristotle, Avicenna and Averroes. As explained in one of his treatises, God is the Eternal Light. God first created *forma prima* and *materia prima*. *Forma prima* is the *Lux*. Coming from a point-like entity, the light - due to its very nature - diffused itself becoming the dimensional form of the matter. Dragged by the light, the matter expanded into the space to create the sphere of a finite universe. From its spherical boundary, the *Lux* created the *Lumen*, the luminosity, which moved inwards, towards the centre of the universe where there is the Earth. In a sequence from the outer sphere to the inner one, each of the nine celestial spheres of heavens is created. The innermost is the sphere of the moon, which produces, through its own *Lumen*, the four spheres consisting of *fire, air, water and earth*. And here, in the part of the world where the four elements of the ancient physics dominate, we have the phenomena on which Grosseteste exercised his medieval science of Nature.

Grosseteste wrote several scientific treatises, mainly concerning physics; in them we can find very interesting thoughts, experiments and phenomena about optics, acoustic, generation of heat and phase transitions. Here we discuss one of the laws of the geometrical optics, proposed in his treatise entitled "De Iride". It is the law of refraction, today given in the proper form by the Snell's law (the discussion here proposed is mainly based on book [Sparavigna, 2016] and books and works given in the list of references). Before discussing Grosseteste's law of refraction, some words about this medieval thinker are necessary.

Grosseteste's scientific thought

Robert Grosseteste was an English philosopher and theologian who became Bishop of Lincoln from 1235 to 1253. For the remarkable scientific treatises that he wrote, Grosseteste was defined by the historian of science Alistair Cameron Crombie, "the real founder of the tradition of scientific thought in medieval Oxford, and in some ways, of the modern English intellectual tradition" [Crombie, 1959]. For his work for the church, upon his death Grosseteste was revered as a saint in England, but attempts to have his canonization failed (more details on his life in the Appendix).

Grosseteste was a master of theology. Among his students we can find the Franciscan Roger Bacon, that gained from the master a profound interest in optics and other sciences. Also John Peckham considered Robert Grosseteste as an inspiration for his studies. Besides lecturing on theology and the Bible, Grosseteste preached within the diocese. A collection of some of his sermons and short reflections is given in a corpus that today is known as Grosseteste's Dicta. Besides the scientific manuscripts, also these and other theological writings, such as the Hexaëmeron written in the 1230s, are revealing his interest in the natural world. He wrote also a "Chateau d'Amour", in French, which is an allegorical poem on the creation of the world and its Christian redemption. However, Grosseteste remains best known because of his treatises concerning what today is called "science" or "physics", written from about 1220 to 1235. Among these treatises the most famous are "De Luce", on his metaphysics of light and cosmogony, and "De Iride", on optics and rainbow.

According to Roger Bacon, Grosseteste played a key role in the development of the science in Oxford. Following Bacon, several scholars [Lewis, 2013, ten Doesschate, 1962, Baur, 1912], remarked that Grosseteste had, consequently, a fundamental role in the Western physics. Crombie, that we have already mentioned, even claimed Grosseteste as the first in the Latin West to develop an account of an experimental method in science, with his systematic use of the method of “experimental verification and falsification” [Crombie, 1955]. It is true, as we can see in reading his treatises, that Grosseteste is often using the “experimentum”. However, it is necessary to tell that Grosseteste’s experimental method was quite different from the modern methods used in controlled experiments.

Actually, Grosseteste derived his conclusions on the basis of a mix of considerations, appealing to authority and to the everyday observation (this was the Latin “experimentum”). He made use of thought experiments and of some certain metaphysical assumptions, such as the principle of the “least action”, that we will find, for instance, in reading his *De Iride*.

Grosseteste was the first thinker that fully understood the Aristotle's thought on the dual path of scientific reasoning. In one way, a scientist generalizes the particular observations into a universal law; then, in the opposite direction, passes from the universal law to the prediction of particular phenomena. Grosseteste defined this approach the "resolution and composition". Moreover, he said that both paths should be verified through “experimenta”. From the Oxonian scholars, through the Oxford Calculators of Merton College, these ideas moved during the following centuries towards Padua and Galileo Galilei, and therefore to the modern science.

Another important Grosseteste’s idea was that of the subordination of the sciences. For instance, when we consider geometry and optics, we have that optics is subordinate to geometry, which is giving the laws governing the rays of light. This means that geometry is the science which is fundamental for the calculations that we need in optics. Knowing the laws and being able of modelling them by means of the geometry, we are able to create any desired instrument, to see the far distant objects or the very small ones, that is, to have telescopes and microscopes. This is precisely what we find in Grosseteste’s *De Iride*.

Following Boethius' arguments, as Grosseteste is explicitly telling, we can conclude that mathematics is the highest of all sciences and the basis for all others. This is in agreements with Grosseteste's Neoplatonic outlook, which considers the light as "forma prima", the first form of all things, the source of the dimensions of the matter and of its motions. Hence, since light propagates in the space through its geometry of lines and points, it can be modelled by geometry, that is, by mathematics. Let us remark that, at Grosseteste's time, mathematics consisted of arithmetic and geometry.

Reflection, Refraction and Optical Instruments

Let us here propose a discussion of Grosseteste's Physics concerning his optics. Then, let us consider one of his most famous treatises, the *De Iride*. As we have told previously, Grosseteste made use of thought experiments and of some assumptions, such as the principle of the "least action", a principle that we will find in this treatise.

In the next section the reader can find some parts of the *De Iride*, from a translation I made in 2012. In spite of the title, the treatise is not only a discussion about the rainbow (in Latin, *Iride*). In fact, in the first part of the text we can read a study of reflection and refraction of light. Besides these phenomena, that Grosseteste discussed also in his treatise entitled *On Lines, Angles and Figures*, we have some words about optical instruments too. In the second part of *De Iride*, Grosseteste continues writing about the rainbow as a phenomenon of refraction of light. Let us tell that Grosseteste imagined the rainbow as the product of a huge optical instrument, consisting of a stratified medium created by the humidity carried by a cloud. He explains how the shape of the rainbow is originated and the creation of its colours. Here in the following some passages from Grosseteste's Treatise.

From De Iride Optics and physics have to speculate on the rainbow. However, the same "what" the physics needs to know, is a "because of what" the optics needs. And in fact, Aristotle, in the book on the meteorology, did not show "because of what", in the sense of

optics, but "what" is the rainbow, which is physics, in a quite short discussion. Hence, here, in this treatise, the "because of what" concerning optics we start to discuss and explain in our manner and time opportunity.

First then, let us say that optics is a science based on the figures of the visual perceptions, and it is subaltern to the science based upon figures and schemes (the geometry), which contains lines and radiating surfaces, being them cast by the radiating sun, or by stars, or by any other radiant body. And it has not to be thought that the going out of visual rays from eyes is only a virtual argument, without any reality, as people, who consider "the part and not the whole", are arguing. But let us note that visible objects are of a nature similar to the nature of the shining and sparkling sun, the radiation of which, combined with the radiation of the external surface of a body, completes the total perspective of vision. ...

Of which (optics), there are three main parts, according to the three ways of transition the rays have to the objects of vision. Either the path of the rays to the visible object is straight through a transparent medium having a specific feature, interposed between who is looking at an object and the object itself. Or, it is ruled by a path directed to a body having a virtual nature, that is, a mirror, reflected by it, back to the object we are seeing. Or it is the passage of the rays through several transparent media of different kinds, where, at the interfaces, the ray is broken and makes an angle, and the ray comes to the object not by a straight path, but by means of several straight lines, having a number of angles at the related interfaces. The first part of this science is named "de visu", the second "about mirrors". The third part is coming in our possession unknown and untouched. We know, however, that Aristotle had discussed this third part, which is the much more difficult one, and the subtlety of which was by far the more remarkable, emerging from the deep heart of Nature. This part of optics, if fully understood, shows us the way in which we can made objects at very long distance appear at very close distance, and large things closely situated appear very small; and small things at a certain distance we can see as large as we want, so that, it is possible for us to read the smallest letters at incredible distance, or count the sand, or grain, or grass, or anything else so minute. In what way, however, it is necessary to understand how this wonder happens; once understood, it will become clear to everybody.

Visual rays, penetrating through several transparent different materials, are broken at interfaces; and the parts of these rays, which we find in the different existing transparent materials, are angularly connected at the interface of them. This, however, is clear by means of an experience, the principle of which is set down in the book on the mirrors: if we cast an object into a vessel, and the distance is assumed that this object may not be seen by us, and some water is poured into, it happens that we can see what is inside (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: The experiment with the vessel, an experiment of refraction.

And the same is displayed by a body having a continuous nature too; therefore, the visual ray, at the interface of two transparent media with different features, must be subjected to a contiguity law. When one total ray is generated from a source, the continuity of it cannot be broken, except when its generation is broken, and at the interface of two transparent media, the ray cannot be discontinuous; at the interface, we cannot have a full continuity and a complete discontinuity and therefore, at each point of the interface the two parts of the ray are, not directly, but angularly connected. But, how large is the angular deviation from the straight path associated to a ray? Let us consider the ray from the eye through the air medium, incident on a second transparent medium, as a straight line to the point, where it is incident on the transparent medium. Then let us make a line deep in the transparent medium, a line that makes equal angles with the surface of transparent medium, that is, normal to the interface. Then, I say that the prolongation of the ray in the second transparent medium is following a line, separating of a certain angle from the normal, angle which is one half of the angle “ i ” obtained as follow. “ i ” is the angle given by the line which is the prolongation of

the ray, without interruption and direct, drawn away from the point of incidence deep into the medium, equal to the angle "i", drawn above the surface of the second transparent medium. So we have determined the amount of the refractive angle of the rays.

We know that there are similar experiments giving the refraction of the rays on mirrors, fitting an angle equal to the angle of incidence (Figure 2). And the same tells us that principle of the philosophy of Nature, namely, that "every action of the Nature is well established, most ordinate, and in the best and shortest manner as it is possible." [This is the principle that today we know as the principle of least action].

Figure 2: Grosseteste's law of reflection and refraction. Calling i the angle of incidence, Grosseteste considered the angle of refraction r equal to $i/2$.

Moreover, the object which is seen through a medium composed of several transparent materials, does not appear to be as truly is, but it is appearing composed by the concurrence of the rays from the eye, continuous and direct, and by the lines starting from the viewed object and falling on the following surface, the nearest to the eye, according to its normal. This is clear to us from experiments and from a similar reasoning that we know: that an object seen in a mirror appears in the concurrence of the propagation of the lines of sight and the lines drawn directly upon the surface of the mirror, normal to this surface (Figure 3).

Figure 3: The plane mirror. A' is a virtual image of A.

It is evident, then, what is the quantity of the angle according to which the ray is broken at the interface between transparent media and where the image of an object appears, arising from several transparent media. Let us add also those principles of optics, which are given by the philosophers studying the natural phenomena. We have the following: given the amount of the angle under which an object is seen, it appears its position and size, according to the order and organization of the rays. It is not the great distance rendering a thing invisible, except by accident, but the smallness of the angle under which it is seen. It is clear that it is possible, using geometrical ratios, knowing the position and the distance of the transparent medium, and knowing the distance from the eye, to tell how an object appears; that is, given its distance and size, it is possible to know the position and the size of the image.

It is also clear how we can design the shape of the transparent medium, in order to have this medium able to receive the rays coming out from the eye, according to the angle we choose, collecting and focusing the rays as we like over the observed objects, whether they are large or small, or everywhere they are, at long or short distances. In such a way, all objects are visible, in the position and of the size given by the device; and large objects can appear short

as we want, and those very short and at a far distance, on the other hand, appear quite large and very perceptible.

And in the third part of optics we have the study of the rainbow. ... For the translation of this part of the treatise, see the Reference 46.

Discussion

As we can see at the beginning of the treatise, Grosseteste is distinguishing optics from physics, that is, from the science of Nature. Physics is the description of the natural phenomena, whereas optics (*perspectiva ars*, in Latin) is the analysis of the reasons of phenomena.

Optics is linked to the visual perception: about it, there were two ancient Greek schools, providing a different explanation of vision. The first was proposing an "emission theory": vision occurs by means of rays emanated from the eyes and received by objects. We can see an object directly, or by means of refracted rays, which come out of the eyes, move in a transparent medium and, after refraction, arrive to the object. Among the others, Euclid and Ptolemy followed this theory. The second school proposed the "intro-mission" approach that sees vision as coming from something, representative of the object, which is entering the eyes. Aristotle and Galen followed this theory, which seems to have some contact with modern theories. In the Grosseteste's treatise, it seems that he had mixed Aristotle's ideas with the out-emission theory, and therefore, in the translation I used simply "emission", when Grosseteste is talking of Aristotle.

In the first part of the treatise, Grosseteste is describing some phenomena that we can obtain with lenses; he seems to describe, for instance, a magnifying glass useful to see the small things or read the small letters in a book. Moreover, he tells that we can made objects at very long distance appear at very close distance, and large objects appear very small, and small things we can see as large as we want. Had he some sort of microscope or telescope? We do not know. In any case, we can suppose that he had some reading stones. A reading stone was

a lens having hemispherical shape, that was placed on a text to magnify the letters, so that people with presbyopia could read them. Reading stones were among the earliest common uses of lenses; they were developed in the VIII century, by Abbas Ibn Firnas. The function of reading stones was replaced by the use of spectacles from late XIII century onwards. Early reading stones were made from rock crystal (quartz) as well as glass.

The earliest written records about lenses date to Ancient Greece. In his play, *The Clouds* (424 BCE), Aristophanes is mentioning a burning-glass, a lens used to focus the sun's rays to produce fire. Pliny the Elder shows that burning-glasses were known to Romans, and mentions what was probably a corrective lens. Nero was said by Pliny to watch the gladiatorial games using an emerald, probably concave to correct for myopia. Pliny is also describing the magnifying effect of a glass globe filled with water.

The Law of Refraction

Very interesting in the Grosseteste's description is the fact that he finds and remarks the reason of these effects in the refractions of the rays. Grosseteste is also proposing a law of refraction. This law is telling that the angle of refraction is one half the angle of incidence. Of course, it is quite different from the Snell's law that we use today, which is containing the trigonometric functions of angles and the refractive indices.

Reflection and refraction of light had been already studied by ancient Greek scientists. The fact that the reflected angle is equal to the incident angle was well known. However, refraction is a more complex phenomenon. Ptolemy found a relationship regarding the angles of refraction; this was an empirical law, fitting figures with experimental data. He measured the refraction from air to water, and water to glass¹. Ptolemy plotted r , the refractive angle, against i , the incident angle, at ten-degree intervals from $i=0$ to $i=80$ degrees. The resulting values of r were in agreement with the sine law. The refraction of light was accurately described by Abu Sad al-Ala ibn Sahl, in the manuscript *On Burning Mirrors and Lenses*, of 984 [Mark Smith, 1999]. Ibn Sahl was a Persian mathematician, physicist and optics engineer

1 Snell's Law, http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Snell's_law

of the Islamic Golden Age promoted by the Abbasid court of Baghdad. He made use of his studies to work out the shapes of lenses that focus light with no geometric aberrations. Ibn Sahl's treatise was used by Alhazen, who wrote in 1021 in his *Book of Optics*.

Ḥasan ibn al-Haytham (c. 965 – c. 1040), Latinized Alhazen, was an Arab scientist, mathematician, astronomer and philosopher, who made significant contributions to optics and visual perception, and the first to explain that vision occurs when some light bounces on an object and then arrives to the observer's eyes [Adamson, 2016]. The law was rediscovered by Thomas Harriot in 1602, who did not publish his results although. In 1621, Willebrord Snellius (Snell) derived a mathematically equivalent form, that remained unpublished during his life. René Descartes independently derived the law in terms of sines in 1637, in his treatise “*Discourse on Method*”.²

After Descartes' solution, Pierre de Fermat proposed the same solution based on his principle of least time, postulating that "light travels between two given points along the path of shortest time." Let us note that, in *De Iride*, after a sentence on the reflection of rays from mirrors, Grosseteste writes a principle of “least action” too, quite before Fermat: *Et idem manifestavit nobis hoc principium philosophiae naturalis, scilicet quod "omnis operatio naturae est modo finitissimo, ordinatissimo, brevissimo et optimo, quo ei possibile est"*.

After the part of the treatise on geometrical optics, where Grosseteste is stressing the fact that if we know the rules followed by the rays of light we can give the position and magnitude of the images of objects, he continues with the description of the rainbow. His theory on the rainbow, such as those of other medieval scholars on it [Lee & Fraser, 2001], are partially coming from the ancient Greek and Roman science, and as we can easily appreciate, from the *Natural History* written by Pliny the Elder [Sparavigna, 2013].

In the *De Iride*, Grosseteste is shortly discussing colours. He continues the analysis of colours in another treatise entitled *De Colore*, which is very short, and probably of the mid-1220s.

In these treatises, Grosseteste tells that colours are created by the purity or impurity of the

2 Snell's Law, http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Snell's_law

transparent medium when light, intense or not, is passing through it. From ancient time, it was well known that a prism can create the colour of the rainbow [Sparavigna, 2012]. However, during the Middle Ages, it was believed they were produced by light mixed with matter. This idea survived until the Newton's experiments on the dispersion of light.

About the Grosseteste's Law of Refraction, let us read again what he told. *I say that the prolongation of the ray in the second transparent medium is following a line, separating of a certain angle from the normal, angle which is one half of the angle "i" obtained as follow. "i" is the angle given by the line which is the prolongation of the ray, without interruption and direct, drawn away from the point of incidence deep into the medium, equal to the angle "i", drawn above the surface of the second transparent medium.*

We know that the result is depending on the refractive index of the transparent media. Let us consider the refraction between air and crown glass. From Snell's law we have $\sin(r) / \sin(i) = n_{air} / n_{glass}$. Angles i and r are the angle of the incident ray and the angle of the refracted ray respectively, measured from the normal of the boundary between glass and air. The angle r of the refracted ray (in degrees) as a function of i is given by the red points in the plot given in Fig.4. The green points represent the values of $i/2$. In the Figure 5, we give the same for water. The difference $(r - i/2)$ as a function of i for crown glass and water is proposed in the Figure 6.

Figure 4: Plots of angle r with respect to angle i for crown glass. Green points represent $i/2$.

Figure 5: The same as in the Figure 4 for water.

Figure 6: The difference $(r - i/2)$ as a function of i .

We have used the crown glass - the glass produced from soda-lime - because it happens to be one of the most common glasses manufactured in the world. From the middle ages, this material was used for window glasses. This glass has a low refractive index, of around 1.5. For this material, the refraction proposed by Grosseteste differs by less than six degrees from that given by Snell's law. The problem, in the Grosseteste's treatise, is the following: it is not mentioned the transparent medium that he used. It is possible, being the crown glass well know and used, that he observed the refraction caused by this glass And probably he also knew that this was the best empirical law of refraction suitable for these glasses.

Appendix

Robert Grosseteste (c. 1175 – 9 October 1253) was Bishop of Lincoln from 1235 to 1253. Little is known of his youth. He may have studied the liberal arts at Hereford, thanks to his connection with William de Vere, Bishop of Hereford, and a recommendation from Gerald of Wales³. Grosseteste became master of arts by 1192 and then acquired a position in the bishop's household. At the death of this patron, Grosseteste disappeared from the historical record for several years. He appeared again in the early thirteenth century as a judge-delegate in Hereford. By 1225, he became deacon of Abbotsley in the diocese of Lincoln.

On that period in his life, scholars have different opinions. Some of them are telling that he began a teaching career in theology at Oxford, whereas some others are telling that he studied theology at the University of Paris too. However, clear evidence is telling that by 1229/30 he was teaching as lector in theology to the Franciscans, who had established a convent in Oxford about 1224. Grosseteste remained in this post until March 1235. Moreover, Hugh of Wells, Bishop of Lincoln, appointed him as Archdeacon of Leicester, gaining a prebend that made him a canon in Lincoln Cathedral. After a severe illness in 1232, Grosseteste resigned all his benefices (Abbotsley and Leicester), but retained the prebend.⁴

Grosseteste was a master of theology and trained the Franciscans in the standard curriculum of the theology taught at university. Besides lecturing on the Bible, Grosseteste preached at the university and within the diocese as well, collecting some of the sermons and short reflections, in a corpus that today is known as his *Dicta*. Besides the scientific manuscripts, also these theological writings are revealing his interest in the natural world.

In February 1235, Hugh of Wells died, and the canons of Lincoln cathedral elected Grosseteste as Bishop. He was consecrated in June at Reading. Being not the subject of studies on Grosseteste science, we do not discuss his activity as bishop. Here, we will just point out that the political activity of Grosseteste can be geo-referenced, that is linked in a network of geographical sites, using the “*Roberti Grosseteste Epistolae*” [Sparavigna, 2016].

3 Robert Grosseteste, Available https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Robert_Grosseteste

4 Archdeacons: Leicester, Available <http://www.british-history.ac.uk/fastiecclesiae/1066-1300/vol3/pp32-35>.

Grosseteste died in the night between 8 and 9 October 1253. He was between seventy and eighty years of age. He is buried in a tomb within Lincoln Cathedral.

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